

Interval Analysis: getting to the heart of what confidence, prediction, and tolerance intervals are

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Abstract

The differences and uses of the three most common intervals used in statistics are not well known. While not surprising in the general populace, it is also the case for many statisticians. Traditional statistical education focuses on confidence intervals. While confidence intervals are important, it is not uncommon for misunderstanding of what they entail. Where do prediction and tolerance intervals fit in? This study performs an in-depth Monte Carlo study comparing the interval types to known populations. Graphical and tabular assessments allow the correct application and understanding of confidence, prediction, and tolerance intervals to be seen. This quantifies their differences and illustrates what can be expected and when to use a given approach. In addition to a generic detailed analysis of interval types, applications to oil & gas pipelines are provided with specific guidance on when to use confidence, prediction, and tolerance intervals to address the application needs.

Key Words: Tolerance interval, Prediction interval, Confidence interval, Pipelines, Oil, Gas

1. Introduction

Three types of intervals are used in statistics: confidence intervals (CI), prediction intervals (PI), and tolerance intervals (TI). These differ in their definitions and typical applications. As such, there can be a lot of confusion about them, and this causes concern on multiple levels. For those just beginning to learn basic statistics, this issue is more obvious. Alas, this is not a topic well understood fully by many seasoned statisticians (Hahn & Meeker, 1991). This publication focuses on three types of intervals mentioned above and only for the normal distribution. Thus, there is no mention of other distributions or non-parametric analysis. The intent is to keep one's focus on the differences of confidence, prediction, and tolerance intervals. To keep the paper succinct, only two-sided intervals are discussed. As has been noted (Ryan 2007) for many learning basic statistics, confidence intervals are the interval analysis topic mainly covered. Some students do receive a brief exposure to least squares regression prediction intervals. Few statisticians have had the opportunity to investigate the application and differences between confidence, prediction, and tolerance intervals. This paper will aid in addressing when each interval type is applicable and what information one can properly obtain from each interval type.

2. Confidence Intervals

Confidence intervals (CI) are a basic component of the introduction to the application of statistics to data. This paper only examines cases where the data follows a normal distribution. In doing so, we skip questions about what type of confidence interval is relevant, e.g., is the data binary leading to a proportion confidence interval. The work presented is based on a single normal population with the goal of creating the correct type of interval for two-tailed applications. Many simulations in R (R Core Team, 2021) have been performed to address this topic.

The focus here is based on 10,000 random confidence intervals for a sample size $n = 50$ with a known normal distribution with mean $\mu = 100$, and standard deviation $\sigma = 10$. Other normal means and standard deviations not shown were used in the R simulations. However, by using a normal we have no loss of generality, and the results are applicable to the entire normal family.

What is the common two-sided confidence interval for a population mean of a normal distribution divulging? The associated confidence interval is

$$\bar{x} \pm t_{\alpha/2, n-1} \cdot \frac{s}{\sqrt{n}}$$

where \bar{x} is the sample mean, s is the sample standard deviation, and s/\sqrt{n} is the standard error of the mean. One error is that the common mean confidence interval should be clearly stated as applying to the population mean and not the sample mean.

An ongoing dilemma is the interpretation of a computed confidence interval. An often-heard incorrect explanation of this interval is that it contains $100*(1-\alpha)$ % of the distribution of the individual values. Next, it is not uncommon to mistakenly say that there is a $100*(1-\alpha)$ % chance that the confidence interval includes the true unknown population mean. A confidence interval does not at all say anything about what percent of the underlying distribution is likely to be covered. The confidence interval does not pertain to the individual observations, but instead is on the population parameter μ . Next any confidence interval either includes or does not include the population parameter of interest that here is μ . Let one randomly pull data from a normal distribution with a known mean and standard deviation and generate 95% two-tailed confidence intervals. Each interval would either contain or not contain μ . On the average around 95% of these random confidence intervals would include the population mean μ . This is a good exercise for introductory simulation students to perform – it really aids the comprehension of what one might say about a confidence interval.

Table 1 shows the mean population coverage for confidence levels 0.80, 0.90, 0.95, and 0.99. As said above this represents 10,000 random confidence intervals for a sample size $n = 50$ with a known normal distribution with mean $\mu = 100$, and standard deviation $\sigma = 10$. Since the two-tailed $t_{\alpha/2, 49}$ increases in value as the confidence level increases (or α decreases), the mean rising in Table 1 (from about 14% in this case) of the population of individual values being covered to a higher value (28% here) is anticipated. But does this help address how much coverage of population is included in the confidence interval? It does not. Indeed, as the sample size increases the projected population coverage declines.

Table 1: Population Coverage by the Confidence Interval based on 10,000 replications

Conf Level	Min.	1st Qu.	Median	Mean	3rd Qu.	Max.
0.80	0.088	0.132	0.142	0.142	0.151	0.200
0.90	0.113	0.169	0.181	0.181	0.193	0.255
0.95	0.134	0.201	0.215	0.215	0.229	0.302
0.99	0.176	0.262	0.280	0.280	0.298	0.389

Given the above caveats on the proper use of confidence intervals, when and where might CI be used? Indeed, CI for population parameters are critical tools in arriving at sound statistical decisions. If they are used in the correct manner and do not get extended beyond their limitations, their use is encouraged. Just do not try to move from statements about the population parameter to individual observation coverage.

3. Prediction Intervals

Both prediction intervals (PI) and tolerance intervals (TI) change the emphasis away from a given population parameter. Their goal is to provide information about the anticipated quantity of individual observations being in the resulting interval rather than the population parameter such as the mean μ . PI and TI are not widely used in most statistical applications though they have much value. It is felt that the limited PI/TI use is due to the lack of exposure and knowledge about what may be suitably gleaned from these latter two interval types. This section focuses on PI.

As alluded earlier, prediction intervals, if covered in statistics classes, are generally limited to least squares regression. In this paper, the prediction interval is not regression focused. Instead, a $100(1-\alpha)$ % two-tailed prediction interval is created with a lower and upper bound centered about the sample mean. The straight-forward formula that follows is not generally taught but of considerable value. The prediction interval adds the standard deviation s of the individual observations to the +/- part of the interval computation.

$$\bar{x} \pm t_{\alpha/2, n-1} \cdot s \cdot \sqrt{1 + \frac{1}{n}}$$

What is labelled PI_SD (Ryan 2007) below replaces the standard error used in CI. Since PI_SD is greater than the standard error, the resulting PI is wider than the confidence interval.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{PI_SD} &= \text{SD} * \text{sqrt}(1/n + 1) \text{ where} \\ \text{SD} &= \text{standard deviation,} \\ n &= \text{sample size of data} \end{aligned}$$

The addition of the standard deviation above is the same approach used in regression PI. It widens the resulting interval to capture the individual observations.

When simulating a $100(1-\alpha)$ % confidence level PI from a given normal population two results develop:

- 1) each PI interval on the average covers $100(1-\alpha)$ % of the underlying normal distribution.
- 2) the average proportion of PI that cover $100(1-\alpha)$ % of the distribution is 50%.

Table 2 shows the population coverage by the prediction interval for various confidence levels. It provides statistics summarizing the range of the population coverage by the prediction interval for each confidence level. Again, this represents 10,000 random prediction intervals for a sample size $n = 50$ with a known normal distribution with mean $\mu = 100$, and standard deviation $\sigma = 10$. For each of the five confidence levels in this table the average population coverage rounds to the desired input confidence level. The iterations illustrate that the mean population coverage is in essence the PI confidence level. That is not unexpected, but how does one use and interpret this. It is not unusual for this finding to be misinterpreted. What a 95% confidence level PI covers is really for the next observation. This is easily confused. A 95% confidence level PI does not imply that with 95% confidence the PI will cover at least 95% of the population. It implies that each new observation pulled from the same underlying normal distribution has (on its own) a 95% probability of being in the PI.

Table 2: Population Coverage by the Prediction Interval

Conf. Level	Min.	1st Qu.	Median	Mean	3rd Qu.	Max.
0.50	0.3386	0.4698	0.4997	0.4993	0.5287	0.6655
0.80	0.5976	0.7699	0.8025	0.7993	0.8316	0.9350
0.90	0.7202	0.8786	0.9037	0.8994	0.9245	0.9827
0.95	0.8049	0.9367	0.9538	0.9496	0.9669	0.9957
0.99	0.9161	0.9868	0.9922	0.9899	0.9955	0.9999

Figure 1 provides a plot of all 10,000 iterations for confidence levels: 0.80, 0.90, 0.95, and 0.99.

Figure 1: Proportion of Population Covered at Confidence Levels 0.80, 0.90, 0.95, and 0.99

The average proportion of PI's that cover at least $100(1-\alpha)\%$ of the distribution depends on the sample size. However, as the sample size increases, the proportion settles at 50%. This can be seen in Figure 2 for various confidence levels.

Figure 2: Proportion of Intervals Covering for Various Confidence and Sample Sizes

From the above plot, it can be seen that the proportion of 99% PI's covering at least 99% of the population is much bigger than 50% for small sample sizes. In fact, we need a large sample size to get this proportion close to 50%. This can be seen in Table 3, which shows the proportion of prediction intervals covering at least 99% of the population as the sample size increases.

Table 3: Proportion of 99% PI's covering at least 99% of the Population

Conf. Level	Sample Size	Proportion of Intervals Covering
0.99	10	0.7761
0.99	50	0.6258
0.99	100	0.5909
0.99	500	0.5411
0.99	1,000	0.5249
0.99	2,000	0.5217
0.99	3,000	0.5099
0.99	4,000	0.5193
0.99	5,000	0.5118
0.99	6,000	0.5008
0.99	7,000	0.5135
0.99	8,000	0.5008
0.99	9,000	0.5113
0.99	10,000	0.5072

Summarizing, a prediction interval covers, on average, $100(1-\alpha)\%$ of the underlying normal distribution, and the average proportion of PI's that cover at least $100(1-\alpha)\%$ of the distribution is 50%. These are more evident as the sample size increases.

4. Tolerance Intervals

If the goal is to develop an interval for a single observation, prediction intervals address this concern. For example, this is reasonable when studying the probability of no failure for a single person's car within a year. A manufacturer on the other hand may want to estimate probable warranty costs across an entire year. Then it is important to develop an interval that with a specified level of confidence covers at least a certain percentage of the car population. This later application is a tolerance interval.

Tolerance intervals give a range of values which contain a certain proportion of the population (p) with a certain degree of confidence ($(100-\alpha)\%$). As such, tolerance intervals require a confidence level as well as a specified proportion for their calculation. For example, a 90% tolerance interval with a 95% confidence level contains, on average, 90% of the population with a 95% confidence level.

Even for normal distributions, calculation of tolerance intervals is more complicated than for confidence intervals or prediction intervals. Nowadays, statistical software packages can compute tolerance intervals. However, exact tolerance intervals take longer to compute. There are several approximate methods proposed in the literature to compute tolerance intervals. For this paper, we used the HE approximation in R from work done by W.G. Howe (Howe, 1969). This approximation defines a 2-sided tolerance interval using the formula:

$$\bar{x} \pm k_2 \cdot s$$

where \bar{x} is the sample mean, s is the sample standard deviation, and

$$k_2 = z_{(1+p)/2} \sqrt{\frac{(n-1)(1+1/n)}{\chi_{(1-\alpha), (n-1)}^2}}$$

Comparing the HE approximation to the exact method no discernable differences were found.

As mentioned above, a 90% tolerance interval with a 95% confidence level contains, on average, 90% of the population with a 95% confidence level. However, the sample size plays an important role in the average proportion of the population contained in the tolerance interval. In Table 4 we can see that for samples of size $n = 50$, the means are higher than the input proportion covered. In this table, the confidence level is fixed at 95% and Prop Covered is the input proportion of the population to be covered by the interval. The values to the right in Table 4 are outputs with the mean bolded to make it stand out.

Table 4: Population Coverage by the Tolerance Interval, 95% Conf. Level for $n = 50$

n	Prop Covered	Min.	1st Qu.	Median	Mean	3rd Qu.	Max.
50	0.80	0.6989	0.8466	0.8748	0.8709	0.8993	0.9706
50	0.90	0.8155	0.9331	0.9510	0.9468	0.9649	0.9948
50	0.95	0.8862	0.9710	0.9810	0.9777	0.9880	0.9991
50	0.99	0.9623	0.9959	0.9980	0.9968	0.9990	1.0000

The over-coverage bias decreases as we increase the sample size. For instance, for a sample of size $n = 500$, the 95% tolerance interval with 95% confidence level covers, on average, 96.09% of the population. Table 5 shows the population coverage by tolerance intervals for various p 's and 95% confidence level when the sample size is 500.

Table 5: Population Coverage by the Tolerance Interval, 95% Conf. Level for $n = 500$

n	Prop Covered	Min.	1st Qu.	Median	Mean	3rd Qu.	Max.
500	0.80	0.7689	0.8143	0.8237	0.8233	0.8328	0.8731
500	0.90	0.8757	0.9106	0.9174	0.9169	0.9237	0.9499
500	0.95	0.9330	0.9570	0.9614	0.9609	0.9653	0.9804
500	0.99	0.9839	0.9922	0.9934	0.9932	0.9945	0.9978

Table 6 shows the population coverage by tolerance intervals for various p 's and 95% confidence level when the sample size is 1,000.

Table 6: Population Coverage by the Tolerance Interval, 95% Conf. Level for $n = 1,000$

n	Prop Covered	Min.	1st Qu.	Median	Mean	3rd Qu.	Max.
1,000	0.80	0.7762	0.8099	0.8167	0.8165	0.8231	0.8498
1,000	0.90	0.8816	0.9073	0.9124	0.9121	0.9169	0.9352
1,000	0.95	0.9372	0.9549	0.9582	0.9579	0.9611	0.9722
1,000	0.99	0.9855	0.9915	0.9925	0.9924	0.9934	0.9962

Table 7 shows the population coverage by tolerance intervals for various p 's and 95% confidence level when the sample size is 5,000.

Table 7: Population Coverage by the Tolerance Interval, 95% Conf. Level for $n = 5,000$

n	Prop Covered	Min.	1st Qu.	Median	Mean	3rd Qu.	Max.
5,000	0.80	0.7902	0.8044	0.8074	0.8074	0.8103	0.8259
5,000	0.90	0.8925	0.9033	0.9055	0.9055	0.9077	0.9189
5,000	0.95	0.9449	0.9522	0.9537	0.9537	0.9551	0.9624
5,000	0.99	0.9883	0.9907	0.9912	0.9912	0.9916	0.9937

The average population coverage by the tolerance interval is shown in Table 8. In this table, both the confidence level and the proportion of the population covered are set at 95%. For a sample of size $n = 10$, the mean coverage is approximately 98.97%. This is more than the expected coverage of 95%. As the sample size increases the mean coverage gets closer to 95%. For a confidence level 95%, we need a sample of size around 1,000 for the average coverage to get within 1% closer to 95%.

Table 8: Mean Population Coverage by Sample Size

n	Confidence Level	Prop Covered	Mean Coverage
10	0.95	0.95	0.9897
50	0.95	0.95	0.9777
100	0.95	0.95	0.9715
500	0.95	0.95	0.9608
1,000	0.95	0.95	0.9579
2,000	0.95	0.95	0.9557
3,000	0.95	0.95	0.9547
4,000	0.95	0.95	0.9540
5,000	0.95	0.95	0.9537
6,000	0.95	0.95	0.9534
7,000	0.95	0.95	0.9531
8,000	0.95	0.95	0.9529
9,000	0.95	0.95	0.9527
10,000	0.95	0.95	0.9526

Figure 3 illustrates the mean coverage by the tolerance interval at 95% confidence level and various population coverages and various sample sizes. For 10,000 samples of sizes 10, 50, 100, 500, 1000 to 10,000 the 50%, 60%, 70%, 80%, 90%, 95%, and 99% tolerance interval at 95% confidence level are constructed. For each tolerance interval the mean percent of the population covered is computed.

Figure 3: Graphic depiction of TI bias as a function of the sample size n

A tolerance interval consists of two values that are required: the proportion of the underlying population to be covered and a specified level of confidence. Through simulations, it was noticed that for small sample sizes the TI covers, on average, more than the pre-specified proportion p . This over-estimation is less severe for higher sample sizes.

5. Connection Between Prediction and Tolerance Intervals

A common interpretation of the prediction interval is that of a range of values within which a single observation will fall. Two proportions (confidence level and the desired minimum proportion of the population) are used to define a tolerance interval. The TI covers *at least* a certain percentage of the population with the specified degree of confidence. For PI only the desired confidence level is chosen. In this section it is shown how the prediction interval relates to the tolerance interval. More precisely, it is shown that for a given p , a TI with 50% confidence level and desired minimum proportion p is approximately equal to a prediction interval for which the confidence level is p .

Recall that a $(100-\alpha)\%$ PI is computed using the formula:

$$\bar{x} \pm t_{\alpha/2, n-1} \cdot s \cdot \sqrt{1 + \frac{1}{n}}$$

and a TI is computed using the formula:

$$\bar{x} \pm z_{(1+p)/2} \cdot s \cdot \sqrt{\frac{(n-1)(1+1/n)}{\chi^2_{(1-\alpha), (n-1)}}}$$

If the confidence level of the PI is the same as the proportion covered by the TI, and the confidence level for the TI is set at 50%, then the two intervals are almost identical.

This can be illustrated in two different ways. First, as $n \rightarrow \infty$ we can see from Figure 4 that $t_{\alpha/2, n-1} \cdot \text{PI_SD}$ and k_2 get closer to $z_{(1+p)/2}$. In this figure p is set to 0.95.

Figure 4: Graphic depiction of k_2 and $t_{\alpha/2, n-1} \cdot \text{PI_SD}$ as a function of the sample size n

Another way to visualize the equality between the two intervals is by looking at some examples. In Figure 5 there are 50 PI and TI intervals. The confidence level of the PI is equal to the population coverage of the TI and the confidence level of the TI is set at 50%. The data consists of 50 samples of size 50 from a population that is normally distributed with mean 100 and standard deviation 10. It can be seen that the TI's are slightly larger than the PI's, but they are very close.

50% Conf.Level TI with 95% Coverage and 95% PI, Sample Size n = 50

Figure 5: Graphic depiction of TI's and PI's, Sample Size 50

For a larger sample size ($n = 500$), the two intervals are almost identical, as can be seen in the plot below (Figure 6.)

Figure 6: Graphic depiction of TI's and PI's, Sample Size 500

In the following two tables the average proportion covered by a prediction interval for various confidence levels and the average proportion covered by a tolerance interval for various p 's and fixed 50% confidence level are shown. The results are based on 10,000 iterations of samples of size $n = 50$ from a population that is normally distributed with mean 10 and standard deviation 10. Table 9 is the same as Table 2. It is included here again to make it easier for the reader.

Table 9: Population Coverage by the Prediction Interval

Conf. Level	Min.	1st Qu.	Median	Mean	3rd Qu.	Max.
0.50	0.3386	0.4698	0.4997	0.4993	0.5287	0.6655
0.80	0.5976	0.7699	0.8025	0.7993	0.8316	0.9350
0.90	0.7202	0.8786	0.9037	0.8994	0.9245	0.9827
0.95	0.8049	0.9367	0.9538	0.9496	0.9669	0.9957
0.99	0.9161	0.9868	0.9922	0.9899	0.9955	0.9999

Table 10 shows summary statistics for population coverage achieved by a 50% confidence level tolerance interval for various p 's.

Table 10 Population Coverage by the Tolerance Interval (50% Confidence Level)

Prop. Covered	Min.	1st Qu.	Median	Mean	3rd Qu.	Max.
0.50	0.3384	0.4695	0.4994	0.4990	0.5284	0.6651
0.80	0.5944	0.7667	0.7994	0.7962	0.8286	0.9331
0.90	0.7143	0.8740	0.8996	0.8953	0.9209	0.9813
0.95	0.7967	0.9318	0.9497	0.9455	0.9636	0.9949
0.99	0.9055	0.9835	0.9899	0.9873	0.9940	0.9998

It can be seen from the two tables that the values in the column “Mean” are approximately equal. More examples showing the connection between these two intervals will be presented in the next section.

6. CI/PI/TI Examples

Different examples from the oil/gas industry are discussed in this section. They involve paired data with the variable analyzed being either the difference of matched values or the ratio of matched values. The data in this publication focuses on the depth of the anomaly in percentage of the wall thickness of the underground pipe. Much of the data involves corrosion growth over time that later leads into identifying areas of the pipeline for potential repair. For each of the analyses, results are given for confidence, prediction, and tolerance intervals.

The examples that follow involve in-line inspection (ILI) and/or field excavation (Field) depths. As an ILI tool moves through the inside of the pipe, different types of anomalies (i.e., internal/external corrosion, cracks, and manufacturing anomalies) are identified from signals detected via transducers riding along the inside pipe wall. For historical reasons, the term pigging is often used to refer to the ILI process. Assessment of the ILI runs for pipelines play a large role in estimating integrity, with anomaly size being fundamentally important in acceptability analyses. Many pipelines are inspected with an ILI tool every five or seven years, depending on the product being transported and the identified threats to the pipeline. Because of the time interval between subsequent inspections, comparing successive surveys can help identify if there is major anomaly growth. ILI data is often noisy with considerable error, but it is currently the most effective way to assess the condition of a given pipeline without excavation of the line.

Field depths of anomalies on pipelines are measured in multiple ways and some methods are more accurate. Regardless of the way the excavation field measurement is done, these measurements also have errors though it is felt to generally be less than ILI data. Excavations of buried pipeline are expensive, and results in much less data to compare ILI to Field as contrasted with ILI to ILI.

The general comparison of this type of data is discussed in a publication on a Power BI Bias app to aid ILI bias assessment (Harper et al, 2022). An output plot of the app with the example data is shown in Figure 7. The Bias app focuses on confidence intervals, but it is a way to visualize the matched pairs that can be further studied with both PI and TI.

Without discussing the details of the Power BI app, Figure 7 shows one of its various outputs. Figure 8 is pulled from Figure 7 to better focus on the two variables (paired difference or paired ratio) studied in this section. Figure 8 highlights in yellow the paired difference ILI – ILI data covered in the next subsection.

Figure 7: Power BI Bias app page “Original, Adjusted in/out spec”

Original data													
Source	Min Adj	Mean Adj	Max Adj	# in Spec	n	Certainty	phat	plower	pupper	Ratio <> 1	Min Ratio	Mean Ratio	Max Ratio
1-1 Pit Match	0.004	0.005	0.005	21874	21963	0.80	1.00	1.00	1.00	Ratio <> 1	1.069	1.075	1.080
Earlier FTC	0.017	0.031	0.045	115	119	0.80	0.97	0.93	0.99	Ratio <> 1	1.078	1.133	1.187

Figure 8: Subset of Figure 7 highlighting confidence intervals for ILI-ILI paired differences

As explained in the Bias app publication, the sample mean of the paired differences is Mean Adj in Figure 8. The 95% confidence interval is (Min Adj, Max Adj) or (0.004, 0.005). This is a tight CI due to the 21,963 matched pairs. The 1–1 Pit Match data sample mean difference is about 0.5% wall thickness. This is not a large average increase between the two ILI runs. This CI reveals nothing on the spread of the individual values. It does indicate limited average depth growth over time, but this is over the full line. This is where process such as DNV’s CGReal (Havlock, 2019) identifies portions of the pipeline that may need remediation.

6.1 Example 1: ILI-ILI paired difference comparison

The first example involves 21,962 matched pairs of ILI data. The two types of ILI runs are magnetic flux (MFL) and ultrasound (UT) with MFL being more common in the United States. An older ILI run will be compared to a more recent newer ILI run using 1-1 matched pairs. In the data analyzed here each pair is a 1-1 ILI match, i.e., one to many matches have been excluded. Comparisons are made in the traditional statistical way of the newer ILI minus the older ILI run for each matched pair. It is also common to study the ratio of the new to old ILI. In this section, the matched difference (newer ILI minus the older ILI) is analyzed. In the Field – ILI sections 6.2 and 6.3 the ratio of the Field to the ILI is analyzed.

Figure 9 is a histogram of the paired differences of the matched new ILI minus the older ILI depth. No assessment of normality is given for this data; however, Figure 9 depicts the data set to be mound shaped like a normal distribution.

Figure 9: Histogram of paired differences for Example 1

Table 11 has many values in 13 rows and can be overwhelming. The 95% confidence interval for the population mean, three PI (50% confidence, 80% confidence, and 95% confidence), and nine TI with all possible combinations for confidence level and coverage for 50%, 80%, and 95% are included. The focus of this section is on PI and TI with little time devoted to the CI. While PI are aimed at the next individual observation and TI focus on covering a designated proportion of the full population, this first example with such a large sample size presents some intriguing results not seen in the smaller data sets in the following sections.

One of the most confusing aspects of PI and TI involves what to compare. It is suggested that the following points be a guideline as to aid proper matching of the PI and TI intervals.

1. PI and TI produce roughly the same intervals for 50% TI confidence level when the TI coverage proportion equals the PI confidence level. The smaller table Table 12 helps with this comparison. In this table (as well as the larger Table 11), the 50% TI confidence level cell is bolded to emphasize this point. In such rows the TI coverage is bolded, color coded, and underlined to match the PI confidence level that will have similar intervals.
2. TI interval widths increase within a given coverage when the confidence level increases. The 50%, 80%, and 95% TI confidence levels for a given coverage are color coded to aid identifying this.

Table 11: (ILI new - ILI old) CI/PI/TI intervals for Example 1

Type	Conf Level	Coverage	Interval
CI	95%		(0.003683, 0.005404)
PI	50%		(-0.0393, 0.0484)
PI	80%		(-0.0788, 0.0879)
PI	95%		(-0.1230, 0.1320)
TI	50%	50%	(-0.03933, 0.04842)
TI	80%	50%	(-0.03951, 0.0486)
TI	95%	50%	(-0.03968, 0.04877)
TI	50%	80%	(-0.07882, 0.08791)
TI	80%	80%	(-0.07916, 0.08825)
TI	95%	80%	(-0.07948, 0.08857)
TI	50%	95%	(-0.12295, 0.13204)
TI	80%	95%	(-0.12347, 0.13256)
TI	95%	95%	(-0.12396, 0.13305)

Table 11 shows the computed intervals for CI/PI/TI. The CI is the tightest of all these and will cover only a small percentage of the observations, but its focus is only on the population mean μ . Unlike a CI with the standard error a function of $\sqrt{1/n}$, the PI and TI interval width cannot be made arbitrarily small.

The color coding in Table 11 is structured to allow comparisons as explained earlier. Examine the four cells shaded light green. The PI confidence level of 50% is expected to be close to the TI 50% confidence level and 50% coverage. With the large sample size $n = 21,962$, only small differences exist between the TI confidence level results for 50% coverage. With smaller samples in subsequent examples, it will be evident that the TI widen as the TI confidence levels increases for a fixed coverage. Similar patterns are seen for the other color cells that correspond to TI coverage of 80% and 95%.

To better emphasize the PI and TI expected close comparisons Table 12 shows how a given PI confidence level results in virtually the same interval as TI 50% confidence level where the coverage equals the PI confidence level. The major point is that the 50% coverage TI will closely match when the TI coverage equals the PI confidence level.

Table 12: ILI new – ILI old PI-TI subset for Example 1

Type	Conf Level	Coverage	Interval
PI	50%		(-0.0393, 0.0484)
PI	80%		(-0.0788, 0.0879)
PI	95%		(-0.1230, 0.1320)
TI	50%	50%	(-0.03933, 0.04842)
TI	50%	80%	(-0.07882, 0.08791)
TI	50%	95%	(-0.12295, 0.13204)

In the previous section it was shown that as n becomes large, TI approach PI. The estimation error approaches zero as n goes to infinity. When n is more moderate, this will not be the case.

With the large sample ($n = 21,963$), the PI are like the TI when the PI confidence level is set to the TI coverage proportion. The TI confidence level results deviate little from each other for a fixed coverage. This will not be the case with the second example with a smaller $n = 119$ sample size in the next section. One major point with this first example is the closeness of the PI/TI intervals for a given coverage. Even if the sample size is not so large (as in the other examples) the PI intervals will be close to the 50% confidence TI intervals when the PI confidence level is matched to the TI coverage proportion.

6.2 Example 2: Field/ILI paired ratio comparisons with $n = 119$ samples

Unlike Section 6.1 on ILI-ILI comparisons with 21,963 matches, the Field-ILI ratios in this section are based on a smaller data set with 119 observations. However, for a given pipeline evaluation, this is much larger than many Field to ILI data sets. Part of this is the expense of each excavation to assess the Field Depth, but it is also based on the condition of the line being evaluated.

As done with the ILI-ILI matched pair differences, no formal appraisal is done to assess the normality of the data seen in Figure 10; however, the data visually does appear to be shaped like a normal distribution. Figure 11 is a subset of the earlier Figure 7 but with the highlighted line focusing on the 119 observations that with the ratio of Field to ILI data.

Figure 10: Histogram of the paired ratio of Field Depth to ILI Depth for Example 2

Source	Min Adj	Mean Adj	Max Adj	# in Spec	n	Certainty	phat	plower	pupper	Ratio <> 1	Min Ratio	Mean Ratio	Max Ratio
1-1 Pit Match	0.004	0.005	0.005	21874	21963	0.80	1.00	1.00	1.00	Ratio <> 1	1.069	1.075	1.080
Earlier FTC	0.017	0.031	0.045	115	119	0.80	0.97	0.93	0.99	Ratio <> 1	1.078	1.133	1.187

Figure 11: Confidence intervals for the ratio Field/ILI paired ratios labeled Earlier FTC for Example 2

Table 13: CI, PI, TI intervals for $n = 119$ matched Field, ILI ratios for Example 2

Type	Conf. Level	Coverage	Interval
CI	95%		(1.0778, 1.1873)
PI	50%		(0.9277, 1.3375)
PI	80%		(0.7423, 1.5228)
PI	95%		(0.5329, 1.7322)
TI	50%	50%	(0.92776, 1.337393)
TI	80%	50%	(0.91593, 1.349223)
TI	95%	50%	(0.903554, 1.361599)
TI	50%	80%	(0.743419, 1.521735)
TI	80%	80%	(0.720941, 1.544212)
TI	95%	80%	(0.697426, 1.567727)
TI	50%	95%	(0.537411, 1.727742)
TI	80%	95%	(0.503035, 1.762118)
TI	95%	95%	(0.467072, 1.798081)

A comparison of Table 13 above to Table 11 in the prior section shows the anticipated changes. Now the PI closely matches the TI only when the TI confidence level is 50% and the PI confidence level is set to the TI coverage proportion. Looking at the TI for a given coverage, it is seen that the TI are wider as the confidence levels increases. The 95% PI (0.53, 1.73) is essentially the same as the 50% confidence and 95% coverage TI interval (0.54, 1.73). For lower TI confidence levels and 95% coverage, the 80% confidence TI is narrower at (0.50, 1.76) and the 50% confidence level is even more narrow at (0.54, 1.73).

What does the above tell one? As stated previously, the CI is not for individual observations. The CI is strictly related to the population parameter μ . The 95% confidence PI (0.53, 1.73) that is essentially the same as the 50% confidence TI with 95% coverage, should be used if the goal was to develop an interval that provides a 95% chance that the next single observation would fall into. Turning to a population (not a single observation) coverage of 80%, then the 80% confidence level TI interval widens as expected with even more widening for the 95% confidence level TI. Care is needed to assess the goal of the study that determines the most appropriate intervals.

6.3 Example 3: Field/ILI paired ratio comparisons with $n = 12$ samples

The third example involves a small data set of only $n = 12$ matched pairs. As with the second example this one focuses on the ratio of the Field measurement to the corresponding matched ILI value. This sample size is too small to assess normality.

The PBI Bias app image below shows the population mean confidence interval of the sample ratios. The CI matches what is presented in Table 14.

Figure 12: Bias app image of Field to ILI data with yellow highlighting of the ratio of Field to ILI for Example 3

Table 14: CI/PI/TI for Example 3

Type	Conf. Level	Coverage	Interval
CI	95%		(0.964, 1.410)
PI	50%		(0.9326, 1.4421)
PI	80%		(0.6893, 1.6854)
PI	95%		(0.3834, 1.9914)
TI	50%	50%	(0.93376, 1.440982)
TI	80%	50%	(0.877341, 1.497401)
TI	95%	50%	(0.802823, 1.571919)
TI	50%	80%	(0.705502, 1.66924)
TI	80%	80%	(0.598304, 1.776437)
TI	95%	80%	(0.456717, 1.918024)
TI	50%	95%	(0.450416, 1.924326)
TI	80%	95%	(0.286471, 2.08827)
TI	95%	95%	(0.069933, 2.304808)

The closeness of the CI and the 50% PI is coincidence likely due to the small $n = 12$ size. With only twelve observations, the 3 PI are reasonably close to the corresponding TI interval. Keep in mind that the 80% PI (0.69, 1.69) should be compared to the 50% confidence level TI with coverage of 80% that has the interval (0.71, 1.67).

On the nine TI for a given coverage, the interval gets wider as the confidence level increases. Keep in mind that this interval is centered around not far from 1.0 (in this case the sample mean of 1.187) since the data analyzed is based on the ratio of Field to ILI unlike the paired difference example 1 of ILI new – ILI old.

5. Summary

Statistical intervals are an integral part of data analysis. Three types of intervals were presented. Confidence intervals (CI) are concerned with the population mean. Prediction intervals (PI) are concerned with a single future observation. Tolerance intervals (TI) cover a minimum of a specified proportion of a population with a desired level of confidence. Confidence intervals are tighter (have less range between the lower and upper bounds) than both PI and TI. PI's are tighter than TI's. A prediction interval covers, on average, $100(1-\alpha)\%$ of the underlying normal distribution, and the average proportion of PI's that cover at least $100(1-\alpha)\%$ of the distribution is 50% as the sample size increases. For a given p , a TI with 50% confidence level and desired minimum proportion p is approximately equal to a prediction interval for which the confidence level is p . The results are based on 10,000 random samples of size $n = 50$ from a normal distribution with mean $\mu = 100$ and standard deviation $\sigma = 10$.

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